

SLAVES TRAGIC LIFE

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Annotation: This article is critical analysis about slaves life and their punishment. Novel which was described slaves life Uncle Tom's Cabin by Harriet Beecher Stowe mentioned and reviews of the book. Also described anti-slaves group in 19 century namely abilitsonists and their movement to end slavery.

Key words: slavery, punishment, inspiration, generation, songs, abolitionist movement, America, Europe, historians, evolution, 8 billion, dynamic and phenomenon.

The history of slavery is a large and untellable story, full of tragedy and cruelty that spans both centuries and continents.

Slavery... left a painful mark on the history of mankind. Is it a person's fault to be born with black skin??? After all, it's a gift which was given by Allah. But not everyone can correctly interpret this blessing. Like that people lived in Europe in 18 century. They treated slaves as animals. According to them, slaves have no feeling, slaves have no soul to hurt, slaves can work 18-20 hour but never get tired like robots, slaves can live for along time without food. You can punish them with stick whenever you want maybe you are angry or nothing to do for the mistake not worthy to remember. The punishments took many forms, including whippings, torture, mutilation, imprisonment, and being sold away from the plantation. Slaves were even sometimes murdered. The worst thing in this case slaves can't reply you " You have no any right to treat like that!!!" Unfortunately they can't say it. The reason for it if they say like that words one of their family member is sold to other rich person. This means that a slave should live without a member of his family. It looks like as if living without a part of his body. For the rest of his life he should live his every minutes in pangs of conscience. It's the most terrible form of slavery. Can you imagine yourself in this situation? How many days can you live without your mother? Maybe 3 days? A months? A half of year? A year? What about forever? Surely you can't even think about it. It's just impossible! Unfortunately for slaves it's possible. This case isn't news for them. It happens repeatedly. They have such kind of emotions: sadness, anger, irritability, shame, terror, helplessness and numbness. Due to having no any right to clarify their words they express it in music's. Music was a way for slaves to show their feelings whether it was sorrow, joy, inspiration or hope. Songs were passed down from generation to generation throughout slavery. These songs were influenced by African and religious traditions and would later form the basis for what is known as "Negro Spirituals". It breaks my hurt.

Time passed but nobody cared about the fate of the slaves. In the middle of 19 century, Harriet Bicheer Stowe, American author, wrote anti-slavery novel

called Uncle Tom's Cabin or Slavery Life In this novel she displayed all the case of slaves tragic life by main hero uncle Tom. This novel illustrates slavery in South America not only treatment from master to slaves, but also from trivial thing like food. Foods have become the analysis in literature that it can provide much wider interpretation about the story itself. The food can free people and on the other side the food can enslave people these two contrast can be seen in the culinary from Stowe's Uncle Tom's Cabin. Novel could succeed than author expected. Even it's America's president expressed his opinion about novel. Harriet Beecher Stowe meets with President Lincoln in Washington, D.C., and later describes the visit as "funny." Stowe's 1852 book, Uncle Tom's Cabin, became the second best-selling book of the 19th century, behind only the Holy Bible, and it helped galvanize the abolitionist movement and provided a continuing moral impetus for the North during the Civil War. According to legend, Lincoln tells her, "so you are the little woman who wrote the book that started this great war."

In a week, the novel was sold in 300,000 copy. It updated at that times record. From this novel people started to think about slaves life. Some got inspiration and gathered into a group.in America an anti-slavery group appeared and they announced themselves abolitionist. The abolitionists saw slavery as an abomination and an affliction on the United States, making it their goal to eradicate slave ownership. They sent petitions to Congress, ran for political office and inundated people of the South with anti-slavery literature.

The abolitionist movement began as a more organized, radical and immediate effort to end slavery than earlier campaigns. It officially emerged around 1830. Historians believe ideas set forth during the religious movement known as the Second Great Awakening inspired abolitionists to rise up against slavery. Historians believe ideas set forth during the religious movement known as the Second Great Awakening inspired abolitionists to rise up against slavery.

It's clear that the hard work of abolitionists took a long time. The reason for it slavery system wasn't appeared a day before. Slavery is an appalling practice that has existed since the origins of human history. Although at many points in history, liberators have worked to free specific groups of people, the Abolitionist Movement was different, as it aimed to put an end to slavery as practice. Their action in United States was an attempt to eliminate slavery in a country that valued individual liberty and believed that "all men are created equal." Slave owners dug in as abolitionists became louder in their demands, aggravating regional tensions that eventually led to the American Civil War. Abilitsionists tried a lot. They did their best. But it was clear that this fight is unfinishable. It lasts forever. They could help million of black skins . But this system is even moneymaking industry for some riches. Today in Africa, America, Uerope and

even in Northern Korea there are also slaves. No international agreement has been completely effective in reducing slavery. This stems in part from the evolution of slavery agreements and the inclination on the part of the authors of conventions to include other practices as part of the slavery definition, resulting in a confusion of the practices and definitions of slavery. What has been missing is a classification that is dynamic and yet sufficiently universal to identify slavery no matter how it evolves. We have attempted to build on theories and examples to clarify the identification of slavery by focusing on an irreducible core of three elements. Assessing the presence of all three can then be applied to a variety of social relationships: first, the complete control of one person by another; second, appropriation of labor power; and third, the enforcement of these conditions by threats or acts of violence. Many practices identified in international agreements have some but not all of these three aspects; all three are present in traditional forms of slavery, bonded labor, forced prostitution, and sexual slavery. Effective research and legislation against slavery is important, as it affects an estimated about 8 billion people worldwide, and as slavery is on the increase now that many developing countries are forced to compete for income in a global economy. Finally it is important to remember that slavery, like all social and economic relationships, evolves over time. Any definition that is based on a historical form of slavery will soon lose its power to capture new forms of slavery within its aegis. Our understanding and our definition of slavery must become as dynamic as the phenomenon itself.